

MUSIC THEORETICAL SCIENCES IN DEVELOPING CREATIVITY OF FUTURE MUSIC TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article focuses on the content of creativity, the important aspects of creativity in the work of future music teachers. The role of music-theoretical sciences in the development of creativity of future music teachers is discussed.

Key words. Creativity, technology, music, harmony, music analysis, content, essence.

Today, higher education as a leading institution of learning is of special importance in the development of society in the preparation of competitively qualified personnel. Currently, in our country, in higher pedagogical educational institutions, music education majors are taught in state and non-state pre-school educational organizations, general secondary schools, secondary specialized, vocational educational institutions, formation of children as pedagogical staff for music and art schools; To improve their pedagogical and professional skills, professional competence and creativity while preparing them to work in mass media, state administration bodies, state and non-state institutions, and to improve the quality of modern pedagogues of tomorrow is one of the factors that determine the indicator. It is necessary to pay attention to one point, that it is impossible to be creative without facing the essence of creativity, its aspects and various parameters in the process of passing through various stages of creativity. So, it is necessary to focus on various parameters of creativity from the psychological side and try to understand its essence in the development of a creative pedagogue. While T.A. Barisheva studies creativity psychologically, she cites symptom complexes and parameters in the structure of creativity as follows:

1. Motivation;
2. Emotional-creative features;
3. Intellectual parameters;
4. Aesthetic creative qualities and abilities;
5. Communication parameters;
6. Existential creative features;
7. Competence.

Creativity cannot be mastered by training, existing creativity can be developed. For this, "it is necessary to determine the characteristics of an individual person, to have the necessary skills, to face a problem, to create a special environment."¹ Blindly memorizing and processing information does not lead to creative development, but rather, its creative transformation, finding a different meaning in it, a unique interpretation, forming a personal attitude to it, evaluating its importance, effectiveness, creative thinking and creativity leads to development. The future teacher's creative self-development determines the level of his professional development. This does not exclude creative development at all

¹ Ильин Е.П. Психология творчества, креативности, одаренности // Е.П. Ильин. – СПб.: Питер, 2011. – 433 стр.

stages of the future teacher's professional training, on the contrary, creative development from the student will help to achieve the best results in the future professional activity.

The extent to which subjects are mastered at the undergraduate level is important in developing the professional competence and creativity of future music teachers. If we look at the section of sciences, music-theoretical sciences are the main subjects of music education that determine the level of musical literacy.

Music theory is a part of musicology that includes a complex of disciplines dealing with theoretical aspects. Music theory is a generalizing concept of elementary theory of music, harmony, polyphony, musical form, solfeggio, instrumentation, rhythmic sciences.

In the musical education direction of the pedagogic directions of higher educational institutions, the subject "Music theory" is the subject, the purpose of teaching the subject is to educate students' conscious thinking in relation to musical expressiveness and to form the ability to perceive it, to develop the musical outlook of students, formation and development of perception, correct orientation and enrichment of musical-aesthetic taste, development of creative abilities; is to prepare students for practical work as music teachers.

The task of the subject is to provide students with in-depth knowledge in understanding the main means of musical expression and to teach musical and technical skills;

- getting acquainted with the important issues and main problems of the composer's creativity and providing clear understanding of the music system and the harmony that occupies an important place in it;

- to familiarize students with the basic laws of the structure of the form of a musical work, important musical elements, principles of musical development, the function of parts in the form, and to form the skills of analyzing various musical forms;

- to form students' ability to think musically, to hear music, to feel pure intonation, and to develop their musical memory, to educate them to have a sense of mood, rhythm, tempo and style, and to teach them to apply their acquired knowledge in practice.² The subject includes "Theory of Musical Elements", "Harmony", "Analysis of Musical Works" and "Solfeggio".

As long as the future music teacher acquires all musical-theoretical knowledge from the subject of "Music theory" and is able to apply it in a practical way, he can be considered to have sufficient knowledge, skills and qualifications in this subject. During the student's pedagogical activity, the types of activities of classes in primary classes:

1. "Singing as a choir.
2. Music literacy.
3. Listening to music.
4. Performing movements to the music.
5. Accompanying children on musical instruments...

In middle classes, music lessons are conducted on the basis of three types of activities:

1. Singing in chorus.
2. Music literacy.
3. It is important to be creative in organizing such things as listening to music."³

² "Theory of Music". Science program. Tashkent State Pedagogical University. Tashkent 2020, page 2.

³ Sharipova G, Najmekdinov G'. "Music teaching methodology practical". Study guide, "Turon-Iqbal" publishing house. Tashkent., 2014. Page 11.

Taking into account that all types of lesson activities require musical-theoretical knowledge, in order for the future music teacher to demonstrate his professional competence in each type of activity and to have a creative approach to the processes, it is effective to increase his creativity during the bachelor's period by means of musical-theoretical sciences.

It should be emphasized here that every musician, whether he is a musician, a singer or a musicologist, demonstrates practical performance only by mastering the theory of music, that is, the specific theoretical laws of practice, the elements and structure of the piece he is performing. Every activity of music culture lessons at school is based on musical literacy, and in addition to the theory of elements of music, they are inextricably linked with harmony, analysis of musical works, and solfeggio, which is a practical expression of theoretical knowledge.

Possession of singing competence in this type of activity, in addition to other aspects of creativity, requires demonstration of the communicative, i.e. communication, parameter. Taking into account that the choir is a joint creative activity, cooperation, it is appropriate for the teacher to pay attention to the whole team, to take into account the potential of each student, to clearly demonstrate the communicative parameter of creativity in learning, analyzing and summarizing the voice capabilities of others.

If the chosen work causes a lot of difficulty for the students, the teacher should take into account all possibilities. "It is necessary to carefully study the tessitura, range, difficulties in the text, rhythm, harmonic structure."⁴ For this, in the stages of teaching a song in the form of singing as a choir, the teacher must be aware of the theory of musical elements in order to sing the piece, analyze the piece and teach it by dividing it into sentences, the science of music analysis, in order to properly understand the accompaniment, the chords must understand the harmony in order to feel the changes in the content of the sequence, from a harmonic point of view. The most important thing is that in order to demonstrate singing competence, he must have mastered the course of solfeggio very well.

Music literacy is the main educational activity in music culture lessons. First of all, musical literacy is inextricably linked with the course of the theory of elements of music, and it is possible to conduct the lesson more creatively only by clearly demonstrating the intellectual parameter of creativity. Intellectuality is very helpful in mastering theoretical knowledge, logical and mathematical thinking. Because the intellectual parameter of creativity is related to mental functions.

Listening to music is an important activity, in which students consciously understand the characteristics of music, and the psyche of each student is first of all affected by listening to the same music. In music culture lessons, the activity of listening to music is carried out by various methods: demonstration, practical, comparative and oral.⁵ This requires the teacher's ability to listen to music, i.e. competence. The parameter of emotional-creative characteristics is the leader in creativity. In the process of listening to music, through emotions, i.e. feelings, imaginative reality is embodied in the child's mind. It is important for the teacher to accept the emotional processes in it in an understandable way, and for him to look at this type of activity based on a creative approach.

⁴ Artykov T. "Music teaching methodology". "Muharrir" publishing house. Tashkent., 2010. Page 69.

⁵ Sharipova G. Asamova D. Khodjayeva Z. "Methodology of music teaching theory and school repertoire". Tashkent. 2014. Pages 16-17.

Emotionality has a practical value in making an impression on the creative mind, enriching it, organizing listening to music with a creative approach to each of the above-mentioned 4 methods. In this type of activity, the science of analysis of musical works occupies a very wide place. The reason is that talking about the work by the teacher, analyzing it in terms of form, analyzing the work by dividing it into sentences and phrases ensures the mastery of the work from a theoretical point of view.

Elementary school students are distracted and have a high tendency to play. Carrying out actions in accordance with the music in the lesson helps the students to keep the music well in their minds and concentrate their attention. During the lesson, it is recommended to use the following types of movements: stepping to marching music, running, performing dance elements, conducting independent games, expressed by various hand and body movements corresponding to the character of the music. Each movement is first shown by the teacher, and the music that goes with it is listened to, sung, and analyzed so that it is imprinted in the children's memory in advance. It is known from the course of musical-theoretical science "Analysis of musical works" at the bachelor's level that the melody, harmony and rhythm in creating the musical form are of special importance among the means of musical expression. "Rhythm unites various sounds and chords into a whole, and creates from them comprehensible, characteristic groups and a certain degree of isolation. As a result of the merging and interconnection of such similar and different groups, complete ideas - musical themes are created, and whole works are created from themes and their development."⁶ In the process of studying musical-rhythmic movements, the student must develop the competence of musical thinking. Images of music, stages of its development, content can be better conveyed to children through actions through artistic and musical thinking. A creative approach to this type of activity is inextricably linked with the motivational parameter of creativity, and positive readiness in any form of creativity gives a motivational impetus to the formation of the teacher's creativity and the student's creativity.

Of course, the most interesting thing for students in class activities is accompanying children's musical instruments. Seeing a musical instrument live will increase his interest in music culture lessons. Taking into account that children's musical instruments are divided into "instrumental and non-instrumental" instruments, and the teacher can teach children in a practical way only by playing them himself, the professional and technical competence of the teacher in this type of activity is important.

In higher education, a student learns to play musical instruments. Musical-theoretical science "Harmony" has a special place in the performance of musical instruments, i.e., the possession of professional and technical competence and its development. Because in performance, it is necessary to understand the work from the point of view of key, tonality, chords, harmonic cycles, function, functional system, and be able to analyze harmonically. Through the science of harmony, the performance competence of the student continues to increase. The parameter of aesthetic creative qualities and abilities of creativity includes the formation of creativity, the sense of style, increasing the student's creativity through

⁶ "The Form of Music". Sposobin I.V. The first edition in Uzbek according to the sixth Russian edition. "Teacher" publishing house. Tashkent., 1982. Page 27.

the science of harmony. provides a creative approach to the type of activity, taking into account style, creativity, harmonic integrity.

In general, in music culture classes in general education schools, based on the essence of the subject, by using the types of activities in a different way, achieving a whole complex serves to increase the effectiveness of the lesson and increase the interest of children in science. Analyzing that each type of activity is closely related to music-theoretical sciences, we can understand that special attention should be paid to the pedagogue's acquisition of thorough knowledge in these sciences from the bachelor's period.

In the organization of lessons according to the types of activities, the professional competence and creativity of the teacher is the leading factor in enriching traditionalism on the basis of a modern approach, and it is more appropriate if the professional competence and creativity of future music teachers is increased by means of music-theoretical sciences.

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